

Repeated Impact Resistance of Stellite 6 Hardfacing Layer Produced by Gas Metal Arc Welding

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Abstract

Cobalt-chromium-based alloys, such as Stellite 6, exhibit exceptional wear resistance, chemical stability, and thermal stability, making them suitable for demanding industrial applications. However, the manufacturing of components from Stellite 6 is challenging due to the alloy's high hardness and poor machinability. Hardfacing of enhancing layers on components made from a material with superior machinability and/or more desirable bulk properties has been identified as an effective solution to Stellite 6 manufacturing limitations. The advantages of hardfacing by gas metal arc welding include high deposition rates, cost-effectiveness, and the capability to fabricate large-area structures. Recent studies have characterised Stellite 6 produced by this method in terms of its resistance to external thermal, chemical, or certain mechanical factors. However, to date, limited research has investigated its behaviour under repeated impact loading conditions. The present study investigates the impact resistance of an alloy equivalent to Stellite 6 hardfaced by gas metal arc welding onto a steel substrate. Testing was performed in different positions – above the beads and above their overlaps – in order to evaluate potential differences in impact life. The results indicated that, despite minor variations in morphology and mechanical properties between the distinct positions, the impact lifetime was equivalent in both. The findings of this study provide valuable information for the design and utilisation of components hardfaced with Stellite 6 in applications where impact protection is crucial.

1. Introduction

Hardfacing by gas metal arc welding (GMAW) is a highly productive additive manufacturing technique well-suited for depositing relatively thick layers of material. The process, which utilizes gas metal arc welding technology, employs the heat generated by the arc to melt the filler wire and the surface of a component (substrate), thereby forming a clad bead. Successive, partially overlapping beads create a uniform layer, and multiple layers can be deposited to achieve the required thickness or to control the level of dilution. As the GMAW hardfacing is a specific instance of Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing (WAAM), some authors use the terms interchangeably [1–4].

One of the key hardfacing materials processed by GMAW is the alloy Stellite 6 [2, 5]. This cobalt–chromium superalloy is well known for its exceptional wear resistance, corrosion resistance, and thermal stability [2, 6–8]. The Stellite 6 is cobalt-based alloy; cobalt and chromium form cobalt–chromium dendrites, within which interdendritic carbides such as Cr_7C_3 , Cr_3C_2 , and Co-W-C are found [2, 9]. These carbides give Stellite 6 its high hardness and resistance to mechanical loading. However, the carbide network also results in reduced fracture toughness, and the alloy tends to be prone to localized defects. For this reason, it is not suitable for fabricating bulk components [10, 11]. Instead, Stellite 6 is primarily used in powder or wire form as a hardfacing material for surface treatments, such as plasma spraying, laser metal deposition, or GMAW [12–17].

In GMAW hardfacing, Stellite 6 is applied in a wire form. When wire is deposited via an electric arc, the Stellite 6 material becomes diluted with the substrate material, leading to the formation of additional

phases. Steel of various types is one of the most typical substrates [13]. The resulting metallurgical bond between steel and Stellite 6 forms a multiphase alloy, where Stellite 6 incorporates iron and other elements from the steel substrate, while cobalt and chromium may diffuse into the steel [2, 10]. The structural complexity is further complicated by the deposition method itself, in which successive partially overlapping beads thermally influence each other. Variations in thermal history lead to distinct diffusion behavior, microstructural transformations, and the formation of metallurgical interfaces [2, 18].

When used as a hardfacing material, Stellite 6 is employed, for example, to enhance the surface properties of industrial turbines, pump impellers, engines, and similar moving parts [2, 13, 19]. Throughout the operational process, numerous components are exposed to recurrent dynamic and impact loads. Although the impact resistance of Stellite 6 produced by various technologies, such as high-velocity oxygen fuel (HVOF) and gas tungsten arc welding (GTAW), has been studied [20, 21], no peer-reviewed research to date has addressed this property in Stellite 6 deposited by GMAW/WAAM. This gap is particularly relevant given the growing interest in GMAW hardfacing for manufacturing functional wear-resistant components that are exposed to repeated dynamic loading.

The present study aims to address this gap by providing a comprehensive evaluation of the repeated impact resistance of wire-arc cladded Stellite 6 on steel substrate. The spatial variability research focuses on the influence of bead and bead-overlap regions, as well as the isotropy of the impact response within the plane of the surface. This research is supported by morphological, chemical, and mechanical analyses. The results obtained from this study contribute to a deeper understanding of the performance of GMAW-processed Stellite 6 in demanding operational conditions and provide insights for the optimisation of its application in critical industrial components.

2. Experimental

The TPS 320i MIG/MAG source with WF60i Robacta Drive wire feeder (both from Fronius) was used in cold metal transfer (CMT) regime to melt the Co-based filler wire ALUNOX AX-FD Co6 (ERCCoCr-A, Stellite 6 equiv.) with a diameter of 1.2 mm. The ABB IRB 2400 robot holding the arc torch was employed to produce four 120 mm long linear overlapping beads with a 4 mm pitch on a ground 10 mm thick S355MC steel sheet substrate. The torch was angled at 30° from the substrate normal and pushed toward the melt pool. Figure 1 presents the scheme of the experimental setup.

The beads were deposited at a welding speed of 20 mm/s. The average feeding rate, arc current, voltage, and power were 8.3 m/min, 267 A, 17.4 V, and 5.05 kW, respectively. Due to the complexity of the CMT regime, the arc power is not a simple product of electric current and voltage. It continuously changes as high-current and low-current phases take turns, and the heat source calculates the average power over time. Pure argon at a flow rate of 18 l/min prevented oxidation of the melt pool.

After deposition, the cladded sample was cut perpendicularly to the deposition direction (y-z plane), and together with a reference substrate specimen, it underwent metallographic treatment on an MTH device. The surface of the cladded sample was ground to eliminate waviness induced by multiple bead

deposition. Both specimens were then polished in x-y plane to achieve a uniform surface finish. The arithmetic mean surface roughness R_a was determined in accordance with ISO 13565-1 using the Keyence VK-X 1100 laser confocal microscope and reached $(0.10\text{--}0.15) \mu\text{m}$. The cross-section was polished and then etched with the Kalling 2 solution for 50 s to reveal the macrostructure and identify regions of interest for hardness and impact test measurements. Figure 2 illustrates the clad specimen with the designated measurement regions “bead” and “overlap” located above the cladding depth maxima and minima, respectively.

Vickers hardness of the machined surface was measured using the hardness tester Qness 60A + EVO at a load of 9.81 N. At first, two linear measurement series along the x-axis in x-y plane, each consisting of thirteen indents, were performed in both the bead and overlap regions identified in Fig. 2. Due to the limited dimensions of the sample, hardness was measured at two different locations, each time in the same position relative to the bead and overlap. Then, a series of indents was made across all beads along the y-axis, 0.5 mm under the machined surface in y-z cross-section, located in the middle of the specimen length. The spacing of indents was 0.5 mm in each series.

The samples were investigated using an electromagnetically driven dynamic impact tester. The tester operates at impact loads of 200 N, 400 N, and 600 N, which correspond to kinetic energies of 6.98 mJ/imp., 11.46 mJ/imp., and 17.42 mJ/imp., respectively. The impact frequency was set to 8 Hz. The impact indenter was a 5 mm tungsten carbide ball (Ceratzit CTF12E, with surface roughness G10 according to ISO 3290-1). Prior to each test, the indented ball was set to the same height and the ball itself was rotated so that it contacted the sample with the unworn side. The tested samples were subjected to all impact loads (i.e., 200 N, 400 N, and 600 N). Impact loads were utilised to devise a sequence of 1, 10, 100, 500, 1,000, 5,000, 10,000, 50,000, 100,000, and 250,000 impacts in x-y plane along the bead's length, both in the bead and overlap regions described in Fig. 2. The impact load of 600 N was utilized in order to evaluate material isotropy in the plane of the sample surface. Each test condition (i.e., a given number of impacts at a specific impact load) was repeated multiple times to minimise random error. The testing of the reference substrate specimen (bare S355MC steel) involved only one series, as the in-plane anisotropy or structural inhomogeneity was not expected in bulk steel.

The size and morphology of the impact craters were investigated with the Keyence VK-X 1100 laser confocal microscope. Volume of the impact craters was calculated as a rotational paraboloid [20, 22–24]. The critical number of impacts, representing the impact lifetime, was estimated using the crater volume (including the variability of measured values) and crater dimensions according to Engel's three-zone model [25]. In this model, the first zone corresponds to the initial deformation stage, during which the volume increases relatively rapidly as the number of impacts grows. This phase only lasts at the beginning of the process. After the first few to several dozen impacts, the system enters the second zone i.e. the zero wear zone. During this stage, the crater volume increases only slightly, and the energy delivered by the impact tester is dissipated within the material in other ways. Stress fields develop, gradually initiating the movement of material into pile-ups. The microstructure evolves under the influence of stress, which can lead to local hardening. Over time, an increasing proportion of the energy

is dissipated through crack initiation and propagation. Once a critical number of impacts has been exceeded, the material can no longer withstand the incoming energy and undergoes impact fatigue. This process depends on the specimen being tested and may manifest as delamination, cohesive failure of the substrate, random material removal from the impact crater area, or uncontrolled crack propagation around the crater [20, 24–27]. These processes result in a sudden increase in volume, marking the transition of the curve into the third zone.

The chemical composition of the impact crater, as well as that of the non-impacted sample, was analysed using a scanning electron microscope FEI Magellan 400 XHR equipped with AMETEK EDAX Octane Elect Super energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) detector for elemental analysis.

3. Results

Figure 3 shows the cross-section of the ground hardfaced specimen in y-z plane. The clad beads have a casting microstructure. The different levels of etching might indicate varying dendrite spacing and different portions of eutectics, as the cooling rate varies within the bead and diffusion-related processes occur. The cladding exhibited a thickness of (1.74 ± 0.13) mm in the bead regions and a thickness of (1.00 ± 0.10) mm in regions of bead overlap. Black dots under the surface of the specimen are residual indents from the hardness measurement. The dark region under the clad bead represents the heat-affected zone, as was schematically shown in Fig. 2.

Prior to conducting the impact tests, hardness measurements were performed. Figure 4 presents the results of the hardness measured along y-axis in the x-y plane. Despite the presence of local inhomogeneities, which resulted in a scatter of values, no discernible trend appeared in the measurements. It can be stated that the hardness in the perpendicular direction fluctuated around a mean value of (369 ± 15) HV1.

In the direction of specimen y-axis, eight impact tests were conducted under uniform conditions: an impact load of 600 N and a total of 10,000 impacts. These parameters were selected as they represent the maximum values at which the reference steel consistently yielded predictable results in repeated measurements (as discussed later). The number and spacing of the impact sites were chosen to prevent overlap of the impact-induced deformation zones around the craters. The resulting craters were labelled (a) to (h), as illustrated in Fig. 5.

Following the tests, the parameters of the craters were measured, and the crater volumes were calculated. A comparison of the crater volumes (see Fig. 5a) revealed no significant trend; within the error margins, all craters exhibited comparable volumes. This similarity is further demonstrated in Fig. 5b, which compares the selected crater profiles. For clarity, the comparison focuses on four representative craters, selected based on their positions: above a bead, above an overlap, between these two locations, and near the edge of the specimen.

Figure 6 presents the crater from position (h) in Fig. 5. A thorough observation of the crater reveals the presence of cracks on its outer periphery, specifically at the external edge of the pile-ups – the elevated, plastically deformed zones that envelop the crater rim. The pile-ups are also clearly visible in the profile comparison in Fig. 5b. The occurrence of pile-ups can be attributed to the displacement of plastic material, a consequence of the progressive accumulation of shear stress that occurs during repeated impacts. The outward growth of the pile-ups induces tensile stresses on the outer rim of the crater [28]. This tensile stress is regarded as the most probable origin of the cracks observed in Fig. 6. Similar cracks were present in several other craters. As is evident, cracks propagate along the dendrite boundaries.

3.2 Testing in positions “bead” and “overlap”

As a preliminary step, hardness measurements were taken before the impact tests to ascertain potential differences between the bead and overlap positions. Figure 7 presents the results of the hardness measurement series for the bead and overlap positions in two different locations on the sample surface in x-y plane. No clear trend was evident in either position, with variability in hardness around the respective mean values. However, a discrepancy was observed between the measured means. As illustrated in Fig. 7a, the bead position yielded a mean value of (367 ± 6) HV1, while the overlap position exhibited a slightly lower value of (357 ± 5) HV1. As illustrated in Fig. 7b, comparable hardness values were obtained from the second location, with a range of (366 ± 10) HV1 in the bead position and (354 ± 5) HV1 in the overlap position.

The hardness values measured in both positions were lower than those declared by the producer of the filler wire [29] and correspond to a relatively high level of dilution of the wire with the substrate material. The lower hardness of Stellite 6 produced by the GMAW hardfacing is consistent with the observations of other authors [2, 30].

Although the hardness in the overlap position was lower than in both the bead position, this difference did not exceed 3% of the absolute value, which corresponds to the standard deviation measured within the one series. Moreover, the HV1 analysis revealed that the 9.81 N load resulted in an indentation depth of approximately 10–11 μm , as indicated by semi-empirical relationships derived from measured hardness [31]. This finding suggests that the observed variation in hardness is not attributable to the influence of the substrate, given that the substrate is situated at a depth at least 90 times greater than the indentation depth.

The impact response of the Stellite 6 hardfacing layer was examined at two locations that were referred to as the bead and overlap positions. To evaluate this response, the relationship between crater volume and the number of impacts was analysed. This relationship is known as the loading curve. A comparison of loading curves obtained at both positions is shown in Fig. 8. Figures 8a, 8b, and 8c display the results for a load of 600 N, 400 N, and 200 N, respectively.

This threezone distribution from Engel’s model is the most evident in the loading curve shown in Fig. 8a. Both curves display firstzone behaviour up to ten impacts, after which they enter the second zone as the increase in impact crater volume slows down. This trend changes at around 5,000–10,000 impacts, when the crater volume starts to increase again. The expected impact resistance of GMAW hardfaced Stellite 6 on S355MC steel at 600 N lies within this range. As the impact load decreases, the transition to the third zone shifts towards higher numbers of impacts. For an impact load of 400 N, the critical number of impacts is around 10,000. For an impact load of 200 N, the critical number of impacts is unclear, but it is assumed to be greater than 50,000.

Figure 8 shows that the crater volume after the first impact was approximately the same for both positions. However, from that point until the critical number of impacts was reached, the bead position exhibited slightly smaller crater volumes. This is because slightly smaller craters correspond to slightly higher hardness (see Fig. 7a and 7b), as higher material hardness results in lower deformation.

The transition into the third zone is usually linked to the beginning of fatigue-related phenomena. In our case, however, no signs of fatigue, such as random crack propagation, crack networks surrounding the impact crater, or adhesive and cohesive failure, were observed. Therefore, the critical number of impacts was estimated based solely on the point at which a sharp increase in crater volume was first detected relative to the number of impacts. To refine this estimate, we also considered the values corresponding to the sudden growth in crater depth and diameter, since these parameters exhibit a similar trend to crater volume with increasing impact repetitions. Figure 9 shows an example of the evolution of crater depth and diameter with the number of impacts at a load of 600 N. Similar trends were observed for loads of 400 N and 200 N, but these are not displayed here for clarity. In addition to the bead and overlap positions, Fig. 9a compares the crater depth on reference S355MC steel, and Fig. 9b presents the evolution of crater diameters for all three samples.

The estimated critical number of impacts is summarised in Table 1. The overview shows that the dynamic impact lifetime was essentially identical in both positions. The only difference observed was at an impact load of 400 N, which is most likely due to sample inhomogeneities. However, as the values lie within the observed variability of the data, we consider them to be essentially the same. Furthermore, at all three impact load levels, the number of impacts corresponding to the onset of the sharp increase in crater size was higher than for the S355MC steel reference sample.

Table 1
Critical number of impacts.

	200 N	400 N	600 N
Bead	80,000 ± 3,000	41,000 ± 3,000	10,000 ± 500
Overlap	80,000 ± 3,000	43,000 ± 3,000	10,000 ± 500
S355MC steel	45,000 ± 3,000	15,000 ± 1,500	8,000 ± 1,000

Figure 10 shows an example of impact craters corresponding to 100, 1,000, 10,000, and 100,000 impacts. For simplicity, only craters formed under an impact load of 600 N are shown. Figure 10a shows impact craters from the bead position and Fig. 10b shows craters from the overlap position. Figure 10c depicts a series of craters produced under identical conditions on S355MC steel without a Stellite 6 hardfacing layer. Based on the images, the craters formed in the hardfaced sample from both positions were essentially the same. However, those formed in the uncoated steel substrate exhibited significantly greater deformation. This difference became more pronounced with increasing numbers of impacts and was most apparent at 100,000 impacts.

Although the impact craters in the two examined locations appear visually similar and have similar parameters, e.g., 1,000 impacts at 600 N, they differ slightly in shape. As previously mentioned, the profile of the impact craters is that of a rotational paraboloid. This is due to imperfect plastic deformation. The Stellite 6 hardfacing layer on S355MC steel exhibits a non-zero component of elastic deformation. Furthermore, during unloading, the deformed material relaxes, and the residual stresses and the stresses that caused the transport of material into pile-ups influence the flow of material within the impact crater.

To achieve a clearer and more rigorous quantification of these effects, a new parameter is introduced - the ratio of the actual crater volume (a rotational paraboloid) to the volume of an ideal spherical cap. This new parameter is denoted as Impact Volume Ratio (IVR). The closer the IVR is to one, the greater the plastic deformation exhibited by the sample upon impact, and the smaller the amounts of elasticity and material transported to pile-ups, as well as residual stress accumulation. Conversely, a lower IVR indicates less plastic deformation, as well as higher elasticity and material displacement.

Figure 11 shows a comparison of the calculated IVR for the bead (red) and overlap (black) positions. The graphs also show the IVR results for the non-hardfaced S355MC steel sample (blue). At impact loads of 200 N (Fig. 11a) and 400 N (Fig. 11b), the sample exhibited a similar IVR value in both the bead and overlap positions. Furthermore, the IVR values calculated for the non-hardfaced steel at a load of 200 N were the same as those for the steel hardfaced by Stellite 6. A completely different situation was observed at an impact load of 600 N (Fig. 11c). In this case, the behaviour of all three samples was different. The IVR calculated from the impact craters in the bead position remained almost unchanged from 1 to 250,000 impacts. The average IVR value in bead position was 0.41, varying only within a range of $\pm 10\%$. Conversely, the IVR value in the overlap position initially increased from 0.42 to a maximum of 0.55 with 100–1,000 impacts. After that, the IVR values decreased to values similar to those in the bead position. Finally, the IVR of the steel sample increased monotonically with the number of impacts, rising from 0.33 to 0.61.

Some of the impact craters shown in Fig. 10 exhibit dark patches on the surface. A thorough analysis of these patches revealed that they are, in fact, isolated tribolayers. Initially, tribolayers formed as isolated patches following approximately 5,000–10,000 impacts. As the number of impacts increased, these patches merged to form continuous areas. These tribolayers are believed to form in regions where the

movement of the impact ball induces friction and results in localised heating of the surface. This process can be further intensified by microscopic grains of material released from the sample during impact, which act as an abrasive.

Figure 12 shows the chemical analysis of the tribo-layer. The analysis was performed on an impact crater in bead position resulting from 250,000 impacts at an impact load of 200 N. Figure 12 shows a detailed view of the tribolayer on the surface of such a crater. Two areas analysed by EDX are marked in the figure. The tribolayer at the base of the impact crater is denoted as position 1, while the crater's surface is denoted as position 2. The results corresponding to both positions are displayed below.

4. Discussion

Minor differences in mechanical properties above the bead and overlap positions resulted in distinct deformations under repeated impact loading. These deformations were manifested in a divergent evolution of the parameter, designated as IVR. The impact volume ratio (IVR) parameter indicates the extent to which actual deformation deviates from ideal plastic deformation. In an ideal scenario, IVR would be equal to one and only a plastic deformation would occur. However, the real deformation of the impact crater comprises a combination of elastic recovery, material creep, and strain hardening, as well as the possible formation of tribolayers on the crater surface and material transport leading to pile-up formation, among other mass transports caused by residual stress [22, 28]. The extent to which these parameters occur is indicative of the degree to which IVR is less than one.

The observed difference in the IVR between overlap and bead positions at an impact load of 600 N (see Fig. 11c) was likely caused by the lower hardness in the overlap region. According to the basic definition, hardness is the resistance of a material to plastic deformation; therefore, lower hardness leads to greater plastic deformation and, accordingly, to an increased IVR. Lin et al. [2] observed slightly lower hardness in the position over the overlap of the beads. This was discussed as a result of the difference in the cooling process, and thus in the grain size, in the area over the bead overlap. Furthermore, lower hardness may be related to iron dilution during deposition [2]. It is assumed that the combination of these phenomena will be most pronounced at greater depths, near the interface between the hardfacing Stellite 6 and the steel substrate. Therefore, differences in IVR related to hardness were only observed in analyses with the highest interaction volume, i.e., an impact load of 600 N; lower impact loads of 400 N and 200 N were influenced by iron dilution and grain size differences to a much lesser extent, resulting in minimal IVR differences (see Figs. 11a and 11b).

Another parameter that influences IVR is the formation of tribolayer on the impact crater surface. As was shown in Fig. 12, the tribolayer exhibited a noticeable amount of oxygen, consistent with an oxidic composition. Some authors attribute improved wear resistance to analogous oxide tribolayers, and these might even serve as a protective coating [10, 24, 32, 33]. In comparison with non-oxidised surfaces, the oxidic tribolayer exhibited higher hardness but also higher brittleness [24]. The brittle behaviour of the oxide tribolayer in Fig. 12 is apparently the leading cause of the visible cracks.

Figure 10 shows that impact craters formed by a higher number of impacts exhibited the formation of oxidic tribolayers. In the steel samples, these tribolayers tend to form preferentially at the centre of the impact craters. In the case of the hardfacing Stellite 6, tribolayer areas were observed to be evenly distributed across the entire impact crater, rather than primarily in the centre, as was the case with the steel sample. This evenly distributed protective tribolayer slows down further deformation more effectively than a protective tribolayer primarily distributed in the centre of the impact crater. This, coupled with the higher hardness of Stellite 6, is the primary reason why the hardfaced layer showed lower deformation and a smaller IVR than the steel substrate even after exceeding the critical number of impacts (see Fig. 11).

Figure 10 thus confirms that the Stellite 6 hardfacing layer provides mechanical protection to S355MC steel under repeated dynamic loading. Comparing the impact life of wire arc cladded Stellite 6 with that of Stellite 6 prepared by the HVOF method and of comparable thickness reveals that the former has a longer impact life. Daniel et al. reported lower impact lifetimes for HVOF coatings—approximately 8,000 impacts at 400 N and 4,000 impacts at 200 N [20]—whereas our GMAW hardfacing layer endured longer under the same loading conditions. Even when the highest possible impact rates were applied, only visible cracks were observed outside the crater rim. Those cracks were probably caused by tensile stress induced by the pile-up growth. This distinguishes Stellite 6 hardfaced by GMAW from Stellite 6 samples with similar loadings that were prepared using other methods. Samples prepared by thermal spraying exhibited substantial cracking [20]. Furthermore, cracks were also observed in thicker Stellite 6 samples that were welded using the GTAW method [21].

Although minor local differences in IVR and deformation mechanisms—primarily associated with reduced hardness and variations in tribolayer development—were observed between the bead and overlap positions, these differences did not translate into a measurable difference in impact lifetime within the sensitivity of the present tests. On this basis, the Stellite 6 hardfacing layer produced by GMAW can be regarded as providing comparable macroscopic protection against repeated impact loading in both positions, and the overall impact response may therefore be considered effectively isotropic within the plane of the surface under the tested conditions.

5. Conclusion

The hardness and dynamic impact resistance of the Stellite 6 layer deposited on S355MC steel substrate were investigated. Both tests were performed on the polished surface at positions of beads and their overlaps to evaluate the possible effect of bead remelting on the local mechanical properties of the layer. Marginally lower hardness was observed in the area of bead overlaps. From an impact behaviour standpoint, these phenomena affected the deformation of impact craters. It appears that the formation of a tribological oxide layer on the surface of the craters also played a significant role in repeated impact loading, which was most noticeable when comparing the cladding layer with the steel substrate.

Despite these differences, it was found that the impact lifetime remained the same in both positions, even under several impact loads. Impact testing confirmed that the Stellite 6 hardfacing layer on S355MC steel component is in-plane isotropic and its presence significantly increases the component's impact lifetime.

Declarations

Author Contribution

J.D. - impact testing and optical microscopy analysis, H. Š. - mechanical properties and electron microscopy analysis, L.M. - sample preparation; all authors discussed results and contributed to the manuscript preparation.

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Figures

Figure 1

The scheme of the experimental setup

Figure 2

Schematic of the deposited layers with designated measurement regions

Figure 3

The macrostructure of the cladding's cross-section with indicated investigated regions

Figure 4

Vickers hardness along the y-axis

Figure 5

Comparison of (a) the volumes and (b) profiles of the impact crater in the perpendicular direction

Figure 6

Detail view of the cracking outside the impact crater from the Position (h) in Figure 5

Figure 7

Vickers hardness of bead and overlap series measured in x-y plane at two different locations (a, b) of the sample

Figure 8

Comparison of load curves of the positions bead and overlap under the impact load of (a) 600 N, (b) 400 N, and (c) 200 N

Figure 9

Comparison of the evolution of the impact crater (a) depth and (b) diameter of the cladding at the positions bead (red) and overlap (black), and of the S355MC steel substrate (blue), all after the impact

with a load of 600 N. Dotted lines serve as an eye guide

Figure 10

Comparison of impact craters from series bead (a) and overlap (b). For comparison impact craters from steel S355MC (c)

Figure 11

Comparison of impact volume ratio (IVR) calculated for the position bead (red), overlap (black), and for the S355MC steel (blue). The impact loads of 600 N (a), 400 N (b), and 200 N (c). Dotted lines serve as an eye guide

Figure 12

Detail view of the oxidic tribo-layer on the impact crater with marked places of EDX analysis and measured EDX spectra